

**THE CORRELATION BETWEEN STUDENTS' LEARNING STRATEGY AND
STUDENTS' ENGLISH ACHIEVEMENT TO THE EIGHTH GRADE STUDENTS
OF SMPN H. WUKIRSARI**

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Abstract: This study tried to investigate the correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement to the eighth-grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari. There were two problems which discussed in this study. First was there any correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement to the eighth-grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari? Second, what was the percentage of Students' Learning Strategy? The objectives of this study were to find out the percentages of students' learning strategy and to find out the correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement to the eighth-grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari. The method used in this study was correlation research. The population of this study was all of the eighth-grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari in the academic year 2015/2016. The total number of population was 182 students which were distributed into six classes. There were 28 students treated as the sample of the study. The sample was taken through random sampling. In collecting the data of students' learning strategy, the writer used questionnaire by strategy inventory for language learning and in collecting the data of students' English achievement, the writer used students' report score. Then, the technique for analyzing the data, the writer used Spearman Rank Correlation to find out the correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement. Based on the findings, the result of the calculation correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement was 0.542, whereas the coefficient of correlation was 0.318 (obtained > table). So the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted and the null hypothesis (H_o) was rejected, it means that there was a correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement to the eighth-grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari in the academic year of 2015/2016. Finally, the aim of this article was to clarify on students' learning strategy and students' English achievement.

Keywords: *Learning Strategy, English Achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Textbooks hold a very important role in the teaching and learning process as they are the main references for teachers to conduct the instruction activities in the classroom. Pinter (2006) states that textbook is the most important teaching and learning material that guides teacher's and learner's activities in many classrooms. Many teachers follow every contents and exercise provided in the textbooks they use. Sheldon (1988) and Hutchinson (1994) (as quoted by Wang, 1998) confirm that ELT (English Language Teaching) program really depends on what is served by the textbooks.

That vital role of textbooks creates a huge demand for textbooks evaluation to optimize the learning activities (Wang, 1998). Many experts have formulated the aspects of textbook evaluation. For example, Madjid (2002) from many sources synthesized 10 aspects of textbook evaluation: soundness of theory underpinning the learning principles, cultural and gender bias relevancy, acceptability, authenticity, skills integration, meaningful activity, authentic language use, cognitive development, grammatical and other linguistics explanation – inductive or deductive, and contextual and situational vocabulary presentation.

Focusing on the second point, cultural and gender bias, Nunan (1991, in Madjid, 2002) points out that it is very possible to evaluate learning materials for their sexism and racism contents. In fact, there have been so many studies which are completed which investigate the representation of gender in school textbooks. For instance, Hellinger (1980) in Germany and Gaff (1982) in U.K. who conduct a research on ELT textbooks in their countries and discovered an obvious sexist language patterns which are tied in the textbooks. In the Middle East and Eastern countries, Ansary and Babii (2003) in Iran and also Otlowski (2003) in Japan report that ELT textbooks still portray women in a stereotyped portrayal of mothers and homemakers.

The imbalance gender treatment has long been found not only in school textbooks but also in the daily teachers-students interaction. It is discovered that teachers interact more with male students; listen to them more, call them more frequently, and discuss academic work and career ambitions more than to the female students. Teachers also recognize male students' achievement more than females'; ask boys more challenging question, and give them more accurate feedback. In giving feed back and encouragement, teachers encourage male and female students differently. Teachers encourage male students for their independence, self-assertion, and activity. Meanwhile, they reward female students for their dependence, quietness, deference, and frown on assertiveness (Horgan, 1995).

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Correlation

Richards's et. al (2010: 139), correlation is a measure of the strength of the relationship or association between two or more sets of data. Correlational research comprises of collecting data to determine whether, and to what extent, a relationship exists between two or more

variables. The study of the correlation between or among variables which may have influence is important to increase the effectiveness of time, especially in a learning activity. Saudjana and Ibrahim (2007:77), correlation research is a study about the relationship between two variables or more which is how far the variance in a variable correlate to other variance in a variable. The associational study is also correlational research, conduct the relationship between two or more variables (Syaodih, 2007:79). In this study, the correlation is to measure the relationship between two variables, they are students' learning strategies and students' English achievement.

Learning Strategy

According to Azumi (2008: 151), learning strategies are what learner can use consciously according to need and then allow them to become more responsibility and self-directed. Learning strategies have the possibility to make learning easier and contribute to language acquisition (competence and performance). Moreover, Chamot (2004: 14) said that learning strategies are the thoughts that students have and actions that they can take assist their comprehension, recall, production, and management of their language learning. In addition (Chamot, 1998:4), Learning strategies are the thoughts that students have and actions that they can take) assist their comprehension, recall, production, and management of their language learning.

Classification of Learning Strategy

Oxford, (2003: 2), divided learning strategy into two major classes; they are direct strategies which consist of cognitive, memory-related, and compensatory strategy whereas indirect strategies consist of meta-cognitive, affective, and social strategy.

English Achievement

According to Richard, et.al (2010:6), achievement is a test which measures how much of a language someone has learned with reference to a particular course of study or program of the institution. As well in English, achievement is a measure to know students ability in English skill. At the end of the view, English achievement ability in English subject at the school of the first and second semester.

Related Previous Study

The study had a relationship to the writers' study which was investigated by Miroslava Blazkova, a student in University of Pardubice, faculty of art and philosophy in 2011 with his title "Language learning strategy in English as a foreign language"

Hypothesis

According to Richards et. Al, (2010: 266-267), the hypothesis is a speculation concerning either observed or expected relationships among phenomena. There are two kinds of hypotheses: A null hypothesis, symbolized by H_0 , and an alternative hypothesis, symbolized by H_a . A null hypothesis is a statement that "No difference exists between groups A and B" or

“There was no correlation between variables A and B”, whereas the alternative hypothesis was an opposite statement that “The mean for group A was higher than that for group B” or “There was a positive correlation between variables A and B”. The hypotheses were tested to compare the result of r obtained and the critical value of r table in a two-tailed test. To find the correlation, the calculation was through Spearman Rank Correlation. If r obtained was higher than the value of r table ($r_{obt} > r_{table}$), the (H_a) was accepted each of alternative hypotheses. It meant that there were a significant relationship between students’ learning strategy and students’ English achievement while if r obtained was lower than the value of r table ($r_{obt} < r_{table}$), the (H_a) was rejected each of alternative hypotheses. It meant that there was no significant relationship between students’ learning strategy and English achievement.

Horgan (1995) points out that the imbalance treatment to male and female students has created a low self-esteem and low future-achievements of female students. Hence, since textbooks have become teachers’ main reference which support and influence the whole learning activities (especially for young learners) the imbalance portrayal of gender in school textbooks should be improved.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Fraenkel and Wallen (2009:328), stated that correlational studies investigate the possibility of relationships between only two variables, although investigations of more than two variables are common. Variable is a trait or quality that can be measured by a test or other kind of data collection instrument (Griffee, 2012:92). In this study, there were two variables, independent variable (variable X) and the dependent variable (variable Y). In this case, the independent variable was students’ learning strategy and the dependent variable is students’ English achievement.

Population and Sample

A population in a study was the group on which information was obtained. The larger group to which one hopes to apply the results is called the population (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009:90). The population of this study was all of the eighth-grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari in the academic year 2015/2016. The total number of population was 182 students which were distributed into six classes. There were 28 students treated as the sample of the study.

Technique for Collecting Data

In collecting the data, the writer used a questionnaire to investigate students’ learning strategy. According to Kothari (2004:100), a questionnaire consists of a number of questions printed or typed in a definite order on a form or set of forms. In this study, we used a questionnaire which is adapted from SILL (Strategy Inventory for Language Learning) version 7.0 (ESL/EFL) by Rebecca L. Oxford 1989. There were 50 statements with no negative questionnaire, and have 5 option which is scored 5 to always true of me, 4 to usually true of me, 3 to somewhat true of

me, 2 to usually not true of me, and 1 to never true of me. It means the highest score is 250 and the lowest score is 50. Those 50 statements consist of 6 sub-variables. They were memory-related learning strategy which consists of 9 statements, cognitive learning strategy which consists of 14 statements, compensatory learning strategy consists of 6 statements, metacognitive learning strategy consist 9 statements, affective learning strategy consist 6 statements, and social learning strategy consist 6 statements. In this study, the writer used students' report book to investigate students' English achievement. The writer took the first semester of eighth grade students of SMPN H. Wukirsari in the academic year of 2015/2016.

Technique for Analyze Data

The obtained data was analyzed through three-technique, they were: 1) technique for analyzing data of learning strategy from questionnaire, 2) technique for analyzing data of percentage students' learning strategy 3) normality data test and 4) Spearman rank correlation formula to find out the correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The scores referred to the responses of eight grade students of SMP Negeri H. Wukirasri to the students' learning strategy questionnaire with checklist scoring 5 to always true of me, 4 to usually true of me, 3 to somewhat true of me, 2 to usually not true of me, and 1 to never true of me. After the scores were tabulated, it was found the total highest score of students' learning strategy was 78.8 and the total lowest score of students' learnings strategy was 63.2 (See Appendix B) and the writer classified students' learning strategy in memory-related, cognitive, compensatory, meta-cognitive, affective and social strategy. In memory-related learning strategy was found the highest score of memory-related learning strategy was 91.1 and the lowest score of memory-related learning strategy was 64.4 (See in appendix B). The highest score of cognitive learning strategy was 92.8 and the lowest score of cognitive learning strategy was 64.2 (See Appendix B), The highest score of compensatory learning strategy was 88.7 and the lowest score of compensatory learning strategy was 40. (See Appendix B). The highest score of meta-cognitive learning strategy was 82.2 and the lowest score of meta-cognitive learning strategy was 46. (See Appendix B). The highest score of affective learning strategy was 73.3 and the lowest score of affective learning strategy was 40. (See Appendix B). The highest score of socio learning strategy was 73.3 and the lowest score of socio learning strategy was 40. (See Appendix B). The most dominant strategy which used by eighth students of SMPN H. Wukirsari was memory-related strategy with 78,25 %, and the lowest strategy was socio strategy which in 54,88 %.

The data of students' English achievement referred to students' report score. The scoring of English achievement was analyzed by two semesters, they were; first semester and second semester. The highest score of students' English achievement was 93, the lowest score of students' English achievement was 77.5 and the average of students' English achievement

was 82.66 (83) (See Appendix B). Based on the English Minimum Mastery Criteria of SMP Negeri H. Wukirsari was 75, There were no students who failed the English Minimum Mastery Criteria of SMP Negeri H. Wukirsari.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the finding and discussion presented in the previous chapter, it could be concluded that there was significant correlation between students' learning strategy and the students' English achievement to the eighth grade students of SMP Negeri H. Wukirsari in academic year 2015/2016 and it was proved by obtained coefficient correlation was higher than table coefficient correlation. The most dominant strategy was a memory-related strategy with 78,25 % and the lowest strategy was socio strategy which in 54,88 %.

The obtained coefficient correlation (0.542) was higher than table coefficient correlation (0.318) or obtained $>$ table. It showed that students' learning strategy gave significantly effect to students' English achievement. Based on the calculation, each coefficient correlation of students' learning strategy was higher than table coefficient correlation. The hypothesis conclusion of each correlation, H_a was accepted and H_o was rejected. It meant that there was a significant correlation between students' learning strategy and students' English achievement to the eighth-grade students of SMP Negeri H. Wukirsari in academic year 2015/2016.

Suggestion

Based on the evidence during this study, the study would like to offer some Suggestion, first to the students, should try to find out the dominant learning strategy and improve the learning strategy to get the best strategy in learning. Second, to the teachers should try to find out the dominant learning strategy in the class to determine the most suitable learning media to students' learning strategy. Third, to another writer, it is suggested that the other researchers can continue the other researches on the correlation of students learning strategy

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